

AN ASSESSMENT OF INFLUENCE OF PEER PRESSURE ON UNWANTED PREGNANCY AMONG YOUNG GIRLS IN RURAL COMMUNITIES OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study was to examine the influence of peer pressure on unwanted teenage pregnancy among young girls in rural communities of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria. The study was conducted in Oron Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Study questions were developed by the researchers accordingly and Social conflict theory (Marxist Based) was employed by the researchers for theoretical framework for the study. Systematic Random Sampling and snowball technique procedures were used to study respondent who considered to elders and custodians of customs and traditional of the people. Questionnaire was used in data collection for this study. The data collected were analysed descriptively. Finding of the study showed that peer pressure is a major factor influencing unwanted pregnancy among rural young girls in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The highest percentage of study respondent agreed to the fact that peer pressure has become a concern for the elders due its negative impacts on the young people in Oron. It was concluded that most of the unwanted pregnancy among teenage girls in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State is as a result of peer pressure or per influence. The researchers recommended among others that parent should educate their children on the negative impacts of peer groups within their localities to rescue their young one from the negative impacts of peer group pressure.

Keywords: unwanted pregnancy, peer pressure, young girls, young girls, and rural communities

Introduction

Unwanted pregnancy is a type of pregnancy that the carrier did not intend to do so at the time of conception. There are many socio-cultural factors that occasion unwanted pregnancy among Nigerian teenagers. Some of these factors include deceit marriage, peer group influence and illiteracy. Unwanted pregnancy has a way of frustrating the life, future and destiny of the victim, putting her under the life experience of pressure from tender age. The experience of motherhood from the age where the girl is culturally too young for motherhood and baby care is a frustrating one. Some of the victims have over the years attempted to abort such unwanted pregnancies. Some of them have succeeded while some have lost their lives in the process. As a result of unwanted pregnancies, Nigeria as a nation has lost a great number of young citizens through abortion. Some of them had to abort the unwanted pregnancy out of fear of what their parents will do to them, others out of fear of stigmatization, while some out of fear of facing a life they were not prepared for and some out of the guilt of betraying the customs of their people. Those who survive abortion have bitter stories of damages of the sex organs while those who refuse to abort have lived the life they would never have thought of in their widest imagination. Marston and Cleland (2004) have argued that in most developing countries more than one-third of all pregnancies are considered unwanted and about 19% end up in abortion, with most of them are often unsafe and account for 13% of all maternal death globally.

A situation whereby parents separate from each other or divorce each other, creates an opportunity where the female children become exposed to sexual abuse of various kinds at tender age and end up as victims of unwanted pregnancy. Broken marriage is a frequent issue in Nigeria today with parents giving no regards to the effects on their children, especially the female ones. Most parents seek their selfish happiness abandoning their children to the life of struggle in the pressure of broken home. Divorce is a complex event that can be viewed from multiple perspectives. For example, sociological research has focused primarily on structural and life course predictors of marital disruption, such as social class, race, and age at first marriage (Bumpass, Martin, & Sweet, 1991; White, 1991). When a marriage breaks either through separation or divorce, the home breaks and when the home breaks, the good life and security of the children break. The break most of the time forces the children to fend for themselves and some of the time fend for their single parent that the child choses to go with after the broken marriage. This situation has forced many Nigerian girls into sexual abuse and violations.

In some cases, the girl child takes to sex trade as survival strategy to feed herself, her single parent and her younger ones in the case of the first child of the parent. This survival struggle has led to many unwanted pregnancies among Nigerian girls. The truth of this case is that most of the parents are responsible for rate of unwanted pregnancy in Nigeria through their inability to manage their marital crises which lead to broken marriages, living their female children unprotected in the hands of sexual abusers.

Statement of the Problem

Growing well, living a good life and having a good marital life at full mature age with children well catered for is the dream of every young teenager in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This dream of the young Nigerians in Oron is being aborted from one teenager to the other by unwanted pregnancy. Unwanted pregnancy has not only cut-off dreams and aspirations of the Oron teenagers; it has also forced them into early

marriages, forceful marriages, early life of pains and frustrations, wrong marriages and most of all untimely death. The experience of unwanted pregnancy in Oron Local Government Area is such that makes the teenager to look helpless because of the various socio-cultural factors that accompany this perilous social problem. Much as the situation described here causes concern, it is pathetic to observe that unwanted pregnancy is crawling into the culture of the people, destroying both the people and their culture. This implies that; such a thing that was once considered to be a taboo among Oron people is gaining acceptance among the people and becoming a norm among the various cultural groups in Oron Local Government Area. The researchers are not disturbed by the occasional teenage pregnancies but by the fact that the society appears to accommodate this social problem. What could have led to this change of attitude, from regarding a thing as evil and now regarding it as normal?

Objective of the Study

This study sought to examine how peer pressure influence unwanted pregnancy among young girls in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Peer Group pressure and unwanted pregnancy

Durkin (1996) argues that peer conformity in young people is most pronounced with respect to style, taste, appearance, ideology, and values. Peer pressure refers to the influence exerted by a peer group in encouraging a person to change his/her attitudes, values in order to conform to group norms (Kirk, 2000). Peer groups are an important socialization agent. According to Castrogiovanni (2002), a peer group is defined as a small group of similar age, fairly close friends, sharing the same activities. Adolescents ask questions relating to social identity theories such as, "Who am I?" and "What do I want out of life?" Feeling to be part of a group, be it be the stereotypical jocks, or punks, allows adolescents to feel like they are on the way to answering some of these questions. Given that adolescents spend twice as much time with peers as compared to parents or other adults is reason enough to study the influence or pressures that peers place on each other.

Peer pressure is also defined as when people of one's own age encourage or urging the person to do something or to keep from doing something else, no matter if the person personally want to do it or not (Ryan, 2000). The more subtle form of peer pressure is known as peer influence, and it involves changing one's behaviour to meet the perceived expectations of others (Burns & Darling, 2002). In general, most teens conform to peer pressure on fairly insignificant things like music, clothing, or hairstyles. Participating in peer group activities is a primary stage of development and adolescents' identities are often closely associated with that of their peers (Santor et al., 2000).

According to Howard (2004), adolescents have always been exposed to peer influence, but the kinds of peer influence that they encounter have changed tremendously in the past years. Peers can influence everything from what an adolescent chooses to wear to whether or not an adolescent engages in drug related or other delinquent behaviour.

According to Lashbrook (2000), adolescents are well aware that they influence each other. Peer influence can provide many positive elements in an adolescent's life. It is important, however, to remember that peer influence can potentially have a deadly impact or other various negative effects. According to Black (2002), peer groups provide a forum where teens construct and reconstruct their identities. Castrogiovanni (2002) stated that at no other

stage of development is one's sense of identity so unstable. A peer labelling process may be contributing to the construction of positive identities for some adolescents but negative identities for others (Downs & Rose, 1991). Unfortunately, members of groups may accept negative labels, incorporate them into their identity, and through the process of secondary deviance, increase levels of deviant behaviour.

It is well established that adolescents are more likely than children or adults to take risks, as evinced by elevated rates of experimentation with alcohol, tobacco, and drugs, unprotected sexual activity, violent and nonviolent crime, and reckless driving (Steinberg, 2008).

Illiteracy and unwanted pregnancy

According to the United Nations' Economic, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO 1989), definition, the illiterate, also known as the non-reader is: a person who cannot, with understanding, read and write a simple statement on his everyday life; and a functionally illiterate is a person who cannot engage in all those activities in which literacy is required for effective functioning of his group and community and also for enabling him to continue to use reading, writing and calculation for his own and the community's development. The illiterate is, therefore, a person for whom the written word or symbol in any language conveys no meaning and who, consequently, cannot use it in any form of communication. The latest data show that the global adult literacy rate was 85% and the youth literacy rate was 91% in 2013. This represents an increase compared to estimates for the reference year 2012, when the adult and youth literacy rates were 84% and 89%, respectively (UNESCO, 2015).

The chain of issues in the society that we live in, the strongest link of that chain is illiteracy. Illiteracy is the mother of all issues as it gives birth to many other issues like poverty, unemployment, child labour, female foeticide, population burst and many more (Aggarwal, 2012). According to UNICEF Education Balance Sheet (2015); Nearly 120 million children of primary school age remain out of school, especially working children; children affected by HIV/AIDS, conflict and disability; children of the poor or of minorities; and rural children. Millions are receiving an education of poor quality. At least one third of the 190 million working children aged 10 to 14 in developing countries have no access to basic education. Funding for education interventions in humanitarian crises remains a low priority. Wang (1995) argues that illiteracy came to be identified as a part of the tragic cycle of underproduction, malnutrition and endemic disease in the underdeveloped countries of the Third World.

According to Adepoju (2012), the most important effect is that illiteracy works as an inhibitor to the society, in other words, the more illiterate people in a country; the harder it will be for the country to progress. Illiteracy not only limits the full development of individuals and their participation in society, but also has recoils throughout life, affecting a person's family environment, limiting access to the benefits of development, and preventing the enjoyment of other human rights.

Theoretical Review

Social Conflict Theory

Many academic researchers believed that for any study to meet up with the relevance in academic field, it must be backed up with theoretical background. Based on this, the

researcher used “the Social Conflict theory” which claims human behaviour in social contexts result from conflicts between competing groups. There can be conflict between two groups of people. This theory is Marxist-based. With teenage pregnancy there can be conflict between the parents of the teens and the teens themselves. Parents and kids are always butting heads. Parents want obedience and control from their kids, while kids want freedom from their parents. Teenage pregnancy can be a form of rebellion. As adopted in this study, the teenagers most of the times get into conflict between themselves and their parents. Either because their parents had broken marriages which introduce them to a life of abuse and suffering or they want to go along with their peers against the wish of their parents or they act in rebellion against their parent' wishes and order due to poverty level of their family. If parents cannot provide for their children, most of these children attempt to provide for themselves, and in the process go against their parents' advice (Akan, 2012). A lot of parents kick their children out after finding out their child is pregnant, or refuse to financially support the child. Some parents can even force their children into abortion even against the teenager's will which can lead to resentment and issues hence, conflict in that family (Karyo, 2012).

Methodology

The study was conducted using the descriptive research design because the study was intended to investigate the relationship between peer's influence and unwanted pregnancy. The study was conducted in Oron. Oron is one of the major cities in the Akwa Ibom State of present-day Nigeria. Oron people share a close ancestral lineage to the Efik people in Cross River State; Ibeno, Uruan, Eastern Obolo in Akwa Ibom State and the Andoni (Obolo) people in Rivers State. The Oron people (Örö) are a major ethnic group in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Oron was split into 3 Local Government Areas of Mbo, Oron and Okobo in 1989. Again in September 1991, Urue Offong/Oruko Local Government Area was carved out of Oron Local Government Area. Finally in December 1996, Udung Uko Local Government Area was further carved out of Oron. Oron is a coastal city in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It is home to the Maritime Academy of Nigeria and the Oron Museum. It has an area of 70 km² and a population of 156,461 at the 2006 census. The postal code of the area is 523. The researcher chooses to concentrate her research on what is known as Oron local government area today after the creation of other local government areas from the old Oron nation.

According to Cooksey and Lokuji (1995), a sampling frame is the list of the entire population from which the sample is to be drawn. Population refers to an aggregate of people or things that a researcher has in mind from which one can obtain information and draw conclusions (Franken and Wallen, 2000). A targeted population for a specific study shares a number of common features. In this study the target population was limited to adults considered to be elders and custodians of history, traditions, and customs in Oron Local Government Area.

A total of 100 participants is the sample size involved in this study. They were randomly considered by the researcher for this study from the villages within Oron Local Government Area. The researchers used questionnaire to accessed information for elders who were considered as key informants capable to answer the study questions. The researchers, analysed data collected through descriptive statistics.

Result

Data Analysis

Data collected from questionnaire shows that most of the teenage pregnant girls in Oron Local Government Area were introduced to sex by their peers. Out of the 100 respondents, 63 (63%) were talked into sex by their peers, who were also teenage boys. Though some of them attest to the fact that some of their teenage girl friends convinced them to accept sex offers from their teenage boy friends as sex will make them test the real life of womanhood and enjoy what the adults do not want them to enjoy. Some of the respondents in a none-formal interaction said that; it was their initial experience of sex with their teenage boy friends that gave them the gut to try sex with other bigger offers who were mostly mature adult men. 26 (26%) of the teenage pregnant girls said that they got to know sex when they were raped in their neighbourhood. Most of them agreed that since after the rape, they were convinced by the rapists that there was no evil in sex but only fear, and they gave into pre-marital sex which led to their unwanted pregnancy. 11 (11%) of the teenage pregnant girls from the data collected said that they chose to go into sex on their own due to the influence of the movies that they watch. This percentage of pregnant teenage girls (11%), said that they were ignorant of the consequences of the pre-marital and unprotected sex, and were blinded by the influence of the pornographic they watch in movies. A percentage comparison of the pregnant teenage girls in Oron Local Government Area shows that most of the pregnant teenage girls were influenced by their peers either by being talked into sex or by rape. A total of 89% of the pregnant teenage girls were said to be influenced by their peers.

Analysis of Data using the Social Conflict Theory

The researcher used “the Social Conflict theory” which claims human behaviour in social contexts results from conflicts between competing groups. There can be conflict between two groups of people. This theory is Marxist-based. With teenage pregnancy there can be conflict between the parents of the teens and the teens themselves. Parents and kids are always butting heads. Teenage pregnancy can be a form of rebellion. As adopted in this study, the teenagers most of the times get into conflict between themselves and their parents.

From the findings of the study, most of the teenage girls became pregnant as a result of conflicts either at home, among their parents, or among their peer groups. Findings have it that most of the teenage pregnant girls chose to get involve in sexual activities as a result of getting away with the conflicts that set into their parental backgrounds such as divorced, separation or cohabitations. Some of them agreed that they chose to get involved in sexual activities in order to provide for themselves since their parents couldn't provide for them and this as always caused conflicts at home. While conflict can be said to be the under-tone force responsible for teenage unwanted pregnancy in Oron Local Government Area, the state of being pregnant by the teenage girls generates another level of social conflict as some parents see that as an opportunity to push the girls to the boy or man believed to be responsible for the pregnancy. While other parents want to show their stands on discipline the girls by allowing them to suffer the pains of early womanhood and motherhood on their own without their assistance. In whatever case, teenage girl unwanted pregnancy in Oron Local Government Area has been a case of social conflict and has generated social conflicts at various levels within the family setting and at the communities' level in Oron Local Government Area.

Discussion of other Major Findings

Most of the elders (75%) of the key informants category in Esin Ufot, Esuk Oro, Eyo Ekung Inyang Eyo Obiosio, and Udung Ulo communities in Oron Local Government Area, agreed that parents bad marital practices greatly influence the lives of their teenage children. They also attest to the fact that many of the teenagers are influenced by their friends of the same age cohort or what they referred to as group-mates which introduce the young girls of the group to sexual behaviour especially as characteristics of the group membership, means of survival, means of exploitation of men, means of independent from poor and careless parents, means of having their money, and means of having a source of livelihood. Most of the elders also agreed that peer pressure has been a major factor influencing teenage pregnancy among the Oro people of Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. These findings agreed with Lashbrook (2000) who posited that adolescents are well aware that they influence each other. Lashbrook explained that peer influence can provide many positive and negative elements in an adolescent's life. It is important, however, to remember that peer influence can potentially have a deadly impact or other various negative effects. Findings also agreed with Black (2002) who posited that peer groups provide a forum where teens construct and reconstruct their identities. Castrogiovanni (2002) also stated that at no other stage of development is one's sense of identity as unstable as the teenage age which makes it open for negative influence. A peer labelling process may be contributing to the construction of positive identities for some adolescents but negative identities for others (Downs & Rose, 1991). Unfortunately, members of groups may accept negative labels, incorporate them into their identity, and through the process of secondary deviance, increase levels of deviant behaviour.

Conclusion

In this study, data were collected and analysed descriptively. The study which sought to examine the socio-cultural factors in unwanted pregnancy among teenage girls in Nigeria: a case study of Oron Local Government Area has the following conclusion in line with the objectives of the study as used by the researcher for the study; the researchers confirmed that there is a positive relationship between peer's influence and unwanted pregnancy among teenage girls in Oron Local Government Area. This was possible through analysing the data collected by the researchers. From the result of the findings, it was confirmed that, out of 100 respondents who were study respondents, 89% confirmed to fact that peer pressure is a strong factor that is contributing to unwanted pregnancy among the Oro young girls especially in the rural communities in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the results of findings and conclusions of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations;

1. Parents should give good time to educate their children on the roles of bad friends and their consequences.
2. Government should see how to ease the economic situation of the masses in order to alleviate the suffering of the people and prevent the follow-up consequences of economic hardship.

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